

pri kazi - polemiki - recenzija

**PREGLED VO SOZDAVAWETO NA
INSTITUCIONALNI OTSISTEM
ZA ZAŠTITA, EDUKACIJA I REHA-
BILITACIJA ZA LICATA SO
INVALIDNOST VO REPUBLIKA
MAKEDONIJA VO PERIODOT
1946-1996**

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Voved

Periodot od sredinata na XIX vek do polovinata na XX vek (1947), odnosno do donesuvaweto na Statutot na Svetskata zdravstvena organizacija, pretstavuva vreme vo koe e sozdavan i izgraduvan ne samo konceptot i odnosot, tuku i institucionalni ot sistem za zaštita, edukacija i rehabilitacija za lica so invalidnost vo svetot. Vo ovoj ednovekoven period se sozdavani institucionalni oblaci za socialna zaštita, specijalno vospitanie i obrazovanie, za profesionalno osposobuvawena ovelica.

Kaj nas, zaal, nema e takvo istorisko iskustvo. Mo`e da se ka`e deka op`testvoto ne be e podgotveno da gi prifat novite ide i vo praktkata da gi vgradi sovremeni te koncepcii za odnosot i zaštitata na populacijata { to so vekovi bila dr`ena na margi ni te od `i votot.

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presentations - arguments - reviews

**SURVEY OF ESTABLISHING
INSTITUTIONAL SYSTEM FOR CARE,
EDUCATION AND REHABILITATION OF
DISABLED PEOPLE IN THE REPUBLIC
OF MACEDONIA IN THE PERIOD
1946-1996**

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Introducion

The period from the middle of the XIX to the middle of the XX century (1947), i.e., till passing the Statute of the World Health Organization, is a period in which not only the concept and the relationship was created and built up but also the institutionalized system for care, education and rehabilitation of disabled people in the world. During this one-century-period, institutional forms of social care, special education, professional training of disabled people were created.

Unfortunately, our country did not have such a historical background. The society was not ready yet to accept the new ideas and to implement in practice the contemporary concepts in regard to the social care of the population that had been for ages on the margins of life.

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Vo pvoeni te godini Republika Makedonija nema{ e institucionalna tradicija i praktika, kadri i nauka, { to se osnovni preduslovi za edna op{ testvena praktika. (1)

Do 1946 godina na teritorijata vo Makedonija nemalo organizirana za{ tita, edukacija i rehabilitacija za lica so invalidnost. I malo samo neorganizirani oblici od filantropsko i samarijansko zgri`uvawe na nezna-itelen broj lica so telesni, setilni i mentalni problemi od razni verski organizacii i crkovni ustanovi. Po vospstavuvawe na op{ testveno-pravni te temel na na{ ata dr`ava, **vo 1946 godina se po-na so socijalno-za{ titni ustanovi za zgri`uvawe na "defektni #lica** (kako { to toga{ se narekuvaa): gluvi, slepi, mentalno retardirani i drugi. Del od niv podocna prerasnaa vo specijalno vospitno-obrazovni ustanovi. Vo me|uvreme se formiraa i ustanovi za rabotno osposobuvawe na lica od opredeleni kategorii i invalidnost.

Pove}e pri~ini ja nametnaa potrebatata od po~nuvawe so socijalnata za{ titna komponenta. Zgri`uvaweto na vozrasnite lica so invalidnost i ni vnoto osposobuvawe za rabota, pretstavuva po~etok na institucionalna za{ titnata ovielica koga se otvori **"Dom za slepi #** vo Bitola vo 1946 godina, vo koj se vr{e e rabotno osposobuvawe. Podocna ovaa aktivnost se pro{iri so otvorawe **"Dom za gluvi #** vo Skopje i **"Dom za vospitno-zapu{teni lica#** vo Saraj, kraj Skopje, odnosno vo Kratovo, dodeka zgri`uvaweto na licata so psihika popre~enost po~na vo du{evnite bolnici vo Demir Hisar i vo Bardovci. Vospitno-obrazovnata komponenta se institucionalizira koga oficijalno, so re{enie na Ministerstvoto za socijalnigri`i, vo avgust 1949 godina, se osnova **"Dom za gluvoneni deca#** (internat so u-ili{te) vo s. Petrovec, kraj Skopje, a vo 1950 godina **"Dom za slepi #** vo Skopje. (2)

In the period after the war, there was no institutional tradition and practice, professional staff and a science as a basic precondition for social practice. (1)

Up to 1946 on the territory of Macedonia there was not organized care, education and rehabilitation of people with disabilities. There were unorganized forms of philanthropic and Samaritan care of insignificant number of people with physical, sensitive and mental problems by different religious organizations and church institutions. After establishing the social and legal foundation of our country, **institutions for social care of "defective" people** (as they were called then): deaf, blind, mentally retarded and others **were established in 1946**. Some of them later became special education institutions. In the meantime, institutions for training people with certain categories of disabilities were founded.

Many reasons imposed the need for the social care component. Taking care of adults with disabilities and their training for work was the beginning of the institutionalized care of these people when **"Home for blind"** was opened in Bitola in 1946. They were also trained for work there. These activities were broadened and **"Home for deaf"** in Skopje and **"Homes for upbringing neglected people"** in Saraj (near Skopje) and in Kratovo were opened, while people with psychic disabilities were hospitalized in mental hospitals in Bardovci and Demir Hisar. The educational component was institutionalized when the Ministry for Social Care with an official decision, in August 1949, founded **"Home for deaf - mute children"** (a boarding school) in Petrovec (near Skopje) and **"Home for blind"** in Skopje (1950). (2)

Klu-ni zaborovi: *inst it uci onal en sis-tem, za{ t it a, edukacija, rehabilit acija, o{ t et en sluh, o{ t et en vid, psi hi ~ka popre~enost, t elesna invalidnost, go-vorna komuni kacija.*

Za{ titnata i obrazovata, a podocna i rehabilitacionata komponenta vo siste-mot u{ te vo po~etokot bea kategorijal no insti tuci onal izirani. Se po~nuva so ot-ovorawe ustanovi za opredel ena kategorija lica so invalidnost: gluvi, slepi, vos-pitno zapu{ teni, a podocna i lica so psi-hi ~ka popre~enost. No, golem broj fakto-ri nametnaa promeni vo pristapot i prak-tikata na insti tuci onal izacijata. Mora{ e da dojde do f uzioni rawe na novootvo-reni te ustanovi za gluvi i slepi vo edna zaedni ~ka ustanova koja, so re{ eni e na Ministerstvoto za socijalni gri `i na Makedonija, vo 1950 godina prerasna vo "Zavod za defektni deca#. Vo u~ebnata 1950/51 godina Zavodot pretstavuva po~e-tok i na insti tuci onal na rabota so logopa-ti, odnosno deca so govorni problemi i deca so psi hi ~ka popre~enost.

"Zavodot za def ektni deca#, koj vo 1951 godina se preseli vo Bitola, stana slo`e-na i nst i tuci ja vo koja se obezbedi ja osnovni komponenti za di f erenci rano insti tu-cional izi rawe na edukativnata i rehabi-litacionata komponenta za rehabilita-cija na lica so i nval i dnost vo zemjata. (3) Zaradi obezbeduvawe uvid vo razvojni ot-proces nu`no e da se dade pregled na raz-vojnata hronologija. Ova go nametnuva i f aktot { to na kategorijalen princip e sozdavan insti tuci onal ni ot sistem za za{ t it a, edukacija i rehabi l i taci ja za li-ca so i nval i dnost vo zemjata.

1. Za{ t it a, obrazovani e, profesional-no osposobuvawe irehabilit acija za lica so o{ t et en sluh (gluvi i nagluvi)

Prva ustanova za deca so posebni obrazovni potrebi vo Republika Makedonija, e "Zavodot za def ektni deca# vo s. Petrovec

Key words: institutionalized system, care, edu-cation, rehabilitation, impaired hearing, im-paired vision, psychic disabilities, physical dis-abilities, speech communication.

The components of care, education and later the component of rehabilitation in the system were even in the beginning categorically institution-alized. It started with the foundation of institu-tions for certain category of people with dis-abilities: deaf, blind, educationally neglected, and later people with psychic disabilities. Many factors imposed changes in the approach and practice of institutionalization. There was a need for merging with the newly opened insti-tutions for deaf and blind in one joined institu-tion, which with the decision of the Ministry for Social Care in Macedonia, in 1950, became "Institute for defective children". In the school year 1950/1951 the Institute started work with children with speech problems and psychic disabilities.

The "Institute for defective children", during 1951 was dislocated in Bitola, became a com-plex institution with basic components for dif-ferential institutionalization of education and rehabilitation components for rehabilitation of people with disabilities. (3)

In order to present an insight in the develop-mental process, it is necessary to provide a sur-vey of the developmental chronology. This is also imposed by the fact that the categorical principle is used in institutionalized system for care, education and rehabilitation of disabled people in our country.

1. Care, education, professional training and rehabilitation of people with imapaired hearing (deaf and hard-of-hearing)

The first institution for children with special education needs in the Republic of Macedonia, as mentioned above, is the "Institute for defec-tive children" in Petrovec,

koj vedna{ potoa (1951) se preseluva vo Bitola. Pri "Zavodot za defektni deca# vo Bitola e sozdadena insti tucional na osnova za za{ tita, predu~ili{ no i osnovno obrazovani e, prof esi onal no orientirawe, osposobuvawe i rehabilitacija za gluvi i nagluvi preku slednite organizacioni edini ci: **Gradinka za gluvi i nagluvi deca; Osnovno u~ili{ te so oddel za gluvi i oddel za nagluvi; Stopanska edinica od otvoren i zatvoren tip; Zanaet~iski pogon (modelarstvo, ~evlarstvo, drvodielstvo, kilinarstvo), zenjodelstvo, gradinarstvo, ~ivinarstvo; Dom internat so ambulanta za zdravstvena za{ tita so izolaciono oddeleni e; Edinica za zanaet~isko profesionalno osposobuvawe i Kabinetska edinica.**

Gradinkata za gluvi i nagluvi deca, vo koja istovremeno e ostvaruvan vospitno-obrazoven i habil itacisko korekcionen proces vrz sovremena rehabi litaciska i nterdisciplinarna osnova, so maksimal na primena na pridobivkite od naukata. **Vo gradinkata se postaveni temelite na teoriskiot i primeniot del na surdologijata i audiologijata kako nau~ni disciplini za rehabilitacija na gluvi i nagluvi deca** Stru~niot tim na ovaa edinica go so~inuvaa defektolozii, psiholozi, lekari, neguvatelki i medicinski sestri.

Osnovnoto u~ili{ te za deca so o{ teten sluh go so~inuvaa tri organizaciski edini ci: Oddel za gluvi deca, Oddel za nagluvi deca i Kabinetska edinica. Vo oddel ite decata se rasporeduvaa vrz osnova na timska dijagnosti~ka obrabotka, a za osnovni klasifikaciski kriteriumi se zemani: vozrasta, inteligencijata, sostojbata na sluhot i govorot, vremeto na nastanuvaweto na o{ tetuvaweto na sluhot i vremeto na opf a}awe na deteto. Rabotata vo oddel ite be{ e organizirana i sproveduvana vrz diferencijalna nastava i korekciono-rehabilitaciska terapevtska programa. Vo Oddelot za gluvi deca be{ e formirana i rabote{ e prvata paralelka za deca so psihi~ka popre~nost.

which was dislocated in Bitola in 1951. At the "Institute for defective children" in Bitola, an institutionalized basis was created for care, preschool and elementary education, professional orientation, training and rehabilitation of deaf and hard-of-hearing through the following institutionalized units: **kindergartens for deaf and hard-of-hearing children; elementary school with departments for deaf and hard-of-hearing; commercial unit of opened and closed type; Trade section (model airplanes making, shoemaking, carpentry, carpet industry) agriculture, gardening, poultry raising; Boarding house with ambulance for health care with isolation section; Unit for vocational training and Cabinet Unit.**

The kinder-garden for deaf and hard-of-hearing children, in which education and habilitation-corrective process on contemporary rehabilitation interdisciplinary basis was carried out with maximal implementation of scientific achievements. **The fundamentals of the theoretical and practical part of surdology and audiology as scientific disciplines of rehabilitation of deaf and hard-of-hearing children were set in the kinder-garden.** The professional team was composed of special teachers, psychologists, doctors and nurses.

The elementary school for children with impaired hearing was composed of three organizational units: **Unit for deaf children, Unit for hard - of - hearing children and Cabinet Unit.** In this units, children were divided according to the diagnosis, but as a basic classification criteria the following was taken into consideration: age, intelligence, the condition of hearing and speech, the time when the impairment occurred and time of acceptance of the child. The work in the Units was organized and implemented with differential teaching and correction-and rehabilitation therapeutic program. The first class of children with psychic disabilities was formed and worked within the Unit for deaf children.

Kabinetska edini ca so-i nuva: audi o lo{ ki kabin et so ve` bal ni so audi toren tretman, f onetski kabin et so akusti~na f onetika i fiziolo{ ka f onetska ve` bal na i surdolo{ ko-audiolo{ ka ambul anta od otvoren ti p.

Edini cata za zanaet~isko-prof esionalno osposobuvawe ovozm`uva{ e: rabotno vospitani e, pretprof esionalno osposobuvawe, prof esionalno orientirawe i osposobuvawe na u-enicite. Del od nejzidata organizaciska struktura, kako i del od nejzidata programa za rabota, podocna stanaa osnova na novata ustanova za rehabilitacija na gluvi mladi nci, koja vo 1955 godina se formira i po~na so rabota vo Skopje, kako Ni`o stru~no zanaet~isko u-ili{te so prakti~na obuka za gluvi mladi nci.

Podocna (1953-1955), otkako od ova ustanova se izdvoija vo zasebni insti tucii za za{tita, obrazovani e i rehabilitacija za gluvi mladi nci, slepi i slabovidni deca i deca so psihi~ka popre~enost, Zavodot prerasha vo specijalizirana defekto{ka ustanova za rehabilitacija samo za gluvi, nagluvi i deca logopati.

Vo 1955 godi na Oddelot za gluvi i nagluvi i oddelot za logopati pri Zavodot prerasha vo specijalizirana logopedsko-surdolo{ka ustanova so naziv "**Zavod za rehabilitacija i korekcija na govorot**" - Bitola, so slednata organizaciska struktura: **laboratoriski oddel, u-ili{te za logopati, ambulanta za logopati, gradinka za gluvi i nagluvi, u-ili{te za gluvi i nagluvi so kabinetska edini ca, stacionar za logopati, internat za gluvi i nagluvi.**

So re{eni eto za formirawe na Zavodot ostvarena insti tucionalizacija na logopedijata, surdologijata i audiologijata, kako podra~ja na op{testvenata praktika vo Republika Makedonija. Navedeni te okolnosti nametnaa kvalitetno nova insti tucionalna struktura vo sistemot za za{titata, edukacijata i rehabilitacijata za gluvi i nagluvi lica. Se sozdade slednata mre`a ustanovi:

The Cabinet Unit was composed of: audio logic cabinet with drill session with auditory treatment, phonetic cabinet with acoustic phonetics and psychological phonetic cabinet with acoustic and physiological phonetic drills as well as surdological and audiological ambulance of open type.

The Unit for trade and professional training provided working education, pre-professional training, students' professional orientation and training.

Part of its organizational structure, as well as its working program, later became a basis for the new institution for rehabilitation of deaf youth, which was established in Skopje in 1955, as a Lower Vocational trade school with practical training of deaf youth.

Later (1953-1955), when institutional for care, education and rehabilitation of deaf youth, blind and with poor vision children and children with psychic disabilities set aside, the Institute became a specialized institution for education and rehabilitation only for deaf, hard-of-hearing and children with speech disabilities.

In 1955 the Unit for deaf and hard-of-hearing children and the Unit for children with speech disabilities at the Institute became a specialized logopedic and surdoaudiologic institution called "**Institute for rehabilitation and speech correction**" - Bitola, with the following organizational structure: **laboratory, school for children with speech disabilities, ambulance, a kinder-garden for deaf and hard-of-hearing, school for deaf and hard-of-hearing with cabinet unit, dispensary for children with speech disabilities, boarding house for deaf and hard-of-hearing.**

The Institute, with the decision for its establishing, started the institutionalization of speech therapy, surdology, and audiology as fields of social practice in the Republic of Macedonia.

The mentioned conditions imposed qualitatively new institutional structure in the system of care, education and rehabilitation of deaf and hard-of-hearing people. The following network was formed:

- "Specijalizirana ustanova za patologija na sluhot i govorot za rehabilitacija na gluvi, nagluvi i logopati # - Skopje;
- "Zavod za rehabilitacija na sluh, govor i glas# - Bitola;
- "Zavod za rehabilitacija na deca so o{ teten sluh# - Bitola;
- "Centar za profesionalna rehabilitacija na mladinci so o{ teten sluh# - Skopje;
- Paralelki za gluvi i nagluvi deca pri redovni u-ili{ ta vo Skopje i Ohrid (3)

2. Rehabilitacija za lica so patolo-gija vo govornat a komuni kacija

Po~etocite na rabota so lica so patolo-gija na govornata komuni kacija vo zemjata datiraat od 1950 godina, koga pri "Zavodot za defektni deca# vo Skopje po~na so rabota prvata logopedaska ambulanta. Logopedskata rabota se insti tucional izi ra pri Zavodot (koga se preseli vo Bitola vo 1951 godina) vo logopedaska organizaci ska edini ca so logopedsko u~i li { te, logopedski laboratorii i stacionar za logopati.

Zavodot za rehabilitacija i korekcija na govorot ne mo`e da go odr`i ~ekorot so vremeneto i mora{e da se transformira vo tri ustanovi:

- **Edukativna ustanova za gluvi i nagluvi vo Bitola;**
- **Logopedski edinic i pri edukativni ustanovi vo zemjata;**
- **Samostojna republi~ka audiolo{ka ustanova vo Skopje.**

Sozdadenite pretpostavki i potrebi nametnaa:

- **Institucionalizirawe na logopedaska praktika vo zemjata so { to dojde do presnuvawe na "Audiolo{kiot centar# vo "Fonijatrisko-audiolo{ki centar# na NRM vo Skopje;**
- **Podocna logopedskata edini ca pri Zavodot za rehabilitacija so o{ teten sluh - Bitola se pripojuva na "Fonijatrisko-**

- "Specialized institution of pathology of hearing and speech for rehabilitation of deaf, hard-of-hearing and people with speech disabilities" – Skopje;
- "Institute for rehabilitation of hearing, speech and voice" – Bitola;
- "Institute for rehabilitation of children with impaired hearing" – Bitola
- "Center for professional rehabilitation of youth with impaired hearing" – Skopje;
- Classes for deaf and hard of hearing children at formal schools in Skopje and Ohrid. (3)

2. Rehabilitation of people with pathology in speech communication

The beginning of work with people with pathology in speech communication in our Country dates from 1950 when the first speech therapy ambulance started work within the "Institute for disabled children" in Skopje. Speech therapy was institutionalized at the Institute (when it was dislocated in Bitola in 1951) as a speech therapy unit with speech therapy school, speech therapy laboratories and dispensary for people with speech disabilities.

The Institute for Rehabilitation and Speech Correction could not keep pace with time and had to transform in three institutions:

- **Education institution for deaf and hard-of-hearing in Bitola;**
- **Speech Therapy units at education institutions in the country;**
- **Independent republic audiological institution in Skopje.**

The assumptions and needs imposed the following:

- **Institutionalization of speech therapy in the country, which developed the "Audiological Center" into "Phoneatric-Audio Center" of People's Republic of Macedonia in Skopje;**
- **Later, the speech therapy unit at the Institute for Rehabilitation of Impaired Hearing in Bitola merged with "Phoneatric - Audio**

audiološki centar# - Skopje i prodol-
`uva da raboti kako dependans na toj cen-
tar;

- Dependansot podocna prerasna vo "Zavod za rehabilitacija na sluh govor i glas# - Bitola, za po nekolku godini da se osamstoi;

- Vo Skopje ostana da raboti kako samostojna ustanovata pod naziv "Zavod za rehabilitacija na sluh, govor i glas# pri Klini~kiot centar vo Skopje. (3)

Pokraj spomnatata specijalizirana dr-
`avna logopediska ustanova, bea formirani i logopedski ambulanti pri zdravstveni i edukativno-defektološki ustanovi vo Skopje, Veles, Bitola, [tip, Kavadarci, Negotino i Kumanovo.

3. Zastita, edukacija i rehabilitacija za lica so otkotet en vid

Otkako se sozdadoa soodvetni prostorni uslovi vo Skopje (1954 godina) Izvr{niot sovet na NRM otvoril "Uili{te za slepi deca#, kako obrazovna defektološka ustanova, za da ja izveduva edukativnata komponenta, odnosno osnovното obrazovanie, vo slo`eniot proces za rehabilitacija na ovaa populacija.

Potrebata za kompletirana rehabilitacijska praktika so slepi i slabovidni deca i mladinci dovede do formirana specijalizirana ustanova za rabotno i profesionalno osposobuvawe. Vo 1959 godina be{e otvoren "Zavod za rabotno osposobuvawe na slepi mladinci# vo s. Dra~evo, kraj Skopje.

Funkcioniraweto na dvete ustanovi za slepi, odvoeni edna od druga, se pokazale neekonomi~no vo iskori{tuvawe na stru~niot kadar, opremata i organiziraweto procesot na profesionalno osposobuvawe poradi oddale~enosta na dvete ustanovi. Trgnuvaj{i od toa, vo 1962 godina dvete ustanovi "Uili{teto za slepi# - Skopje i "Zavodot za profesionalno i rabotno osposobuvawe# - Dra~evo se integrirawe vo

Center" - Skopje and continued work as branch of that center;

- The branch later became "Institute for Rehabilitation of Speech, Hearing and Voice" - Bitola and a few years later it became independent;

- The Institution called "Institute for Rehabilitation of Hearing, Speech and Voice" at the Clinical Center in Skopje continued to work as an independent one. (3)

Besides mentioned specialized state speech therapy institution, speech therapy ambulances were formed at the health and special education and rehabilitation institutions in Skopje, Veles, Bitola, Shtip, Kavadarci, Negotino and Kumanovo.

3. Care, education and rehabilitation of people with impaired vision

When appropriate facilities and conditions were created in Skopje (1954), the Executive Council of People's Republic of Macedonia opened "School for blind children" as special education and rehabilitation institution to carry out the educative component, i.e. elementary education in the complex process of rehabilitation of this population.

The need for completion of rehabilitation practice for blind and with poor vision children and youth imposed establishment of specialized institution for work and professional training. Thus, in 1959 "Institute for Work Training of Blind Youth" was opened in Drachevo, near Skopje.

The functioning of both institutions for blind, working separately, was uneconomical in exploiting professional staff, equipment and organization of professional training process, due to the distance of the two institutions. Thus, in 1962 these two institutions, "School for Blind" in Skopje and "Institute for Professional and Work Training" in Drachevo merged in one institution called "Institute for

edna ustanova pod naziv "Zavod za slepi deca i mladinci" - Skopje.

Otkako be{ e izgraden sovremen objekt, razrabotena organi zacijata i koncepcijata i se sozdadoa osnovni kadrovski i tehni-ko-tehnolo{ ki uslovi, ustanovata pre-rasna vo "Zavod za reabilitacija na deca i mladinci so o{ teten vid" - Skopje i po-na da gi vr{ i dejnosti te: **predu-ili{ -no vospitanie, osnovno obrazovanie, ni-`o mzi-ko obrazovanie, sredno-stru-no obrazovanie, korekciono-rehabilitacionen tretman na vidot, rabotno i profesionalno osposobuvawe.** (4)

Vo strukturata na koncepcijata za op{ tata postavenost na reabilitacijata za lica so invalidnost Zavodot be{ e proektiran kako ustanova { to treba da gi vtemeli i razvie osnovite za reabilitacijata na lica so o{ teten vid, odnosno osnovite na tiflolo{ kata teorija i praktika kaj nas.

4. Za{ tit a, obrazovanie i reabilitacija na telesno invalidni deca i mladinci

Do 1963 godi na nema{ e praktika za organizirana insti tucional na za{ tit a, edukacija i reabilitacija za telesno invalidni deca i mladinci. Vo istata godi na Ortopedskata klinika pri Medici nski ot fakul tet vo Skopje вовede vospitno-obrazovna rabota so deca od predu-ili{ na i osnovno u-ili{ na voзраст, { to bea na podolg medicinski tretman. Isto taka, vo Bolni cata za koskozgl obni zabol uvawa vo Ohrid i vo Zavodot za medicinska reabilitacija vo Skopje, se organizira izveduvawe nastava za hospitalizirani deca-u-ene-nici od I do VIII oddel enie vo podra-ni paralelki, organizirani pri najbliski te redovni u-ili{ ta.

Vo 1971 godi na od Republi -ki ot organ za socijalna politika, Sobranieto na op{ tina Strumica i so materijalna pomo{ na Fondacijata "Sju Rajder" od Anglija, be{ e formirana **specijalizirana ustanova za reabilitacija na telesno invalidni**

Blind Children and Youth" – Skopje.

Later, contemporary premises with developed technical and technological conditions, organization and conception, as well as qualified staff, enabled the institution to become "**Institute for Rehabilitation of Children and Youth with Impaired Vision**" – Skopje. This institution implemented the following activities: **preschool education, elementary school education, lower musical school education, secondary school vocational education, vision correction and rehabilitation treatment, work and professional training.** (6)

According to the structure of conception for general rehabilitation of people with disabilities, the Institute was designed as an institution aimed to develop basics for rehabilitation of people with impaired vision, i.e. basics of tiphological theory and practice in our country.

4. Care, education and rehabilitation for physically disabled children and youth

There was no practice for organized institutionalized care, education and rehabilitation for physically disabled children and youth before 1963. The same year, the Orthopedic Clinic at the Faculty of Medicine in Skopje introduced educational work with preschool and elementary school children who were hospitalized for longer period. The hospital for bone and joint diseases in Ohrid and the Institution for Medical Rehabilitation in Skopje organized teaching process for hospitalized school children from I to VIII grade as branch classes of the closest formal schools.

In 1971, the Republic organ for social policy, Assembly of the municipality of Strumica, financed by Foundation "Sue Ryder" from England, a **specialized institution for rehabilitation of physically disabled**

deca i mladienci vo Bawa Bansko - Strumi --ko. Koncepci skata, organizaci skata, tehni~ko-tehnolo{kata i kadrovskata postavenost obezbeduvaa uslovi za ostvaruvawe na dejnostite: **zgrit`uvawe i smestuvawe, osnovno i sredno obrazovanie, rabotno osposobuvawe i profesionalno okvalifikuvawe, rehabilitaciski tretman (psihomotorna terapija, hidroterapija, fizioterapija, elektroterapija, parafeterapija, balneoterapija) i zdravstvena za{tita.** (4)

5. Za{tita, edukacija i rehabilitacija za lica so psihi~ka popre~enost

Institucionalniot sistem za za{tita, edukacija i rehabilitacija za lica so lesna, umerena, te{ka i dlaboka psihi~ka popre~enost }e se prikaz`e spored institucijite {to se osnovani za niv.

OSNOVNO OBRAZOVANIE ZA DECA SO LESNA PSIHI ^KA POPRE^ENOST

Oddelenijata za deca so psihi~ka popre~enost {to rabotea vo "Zavodot za defektni deca" vo Bitola, poradi nepostoewe soodvetni uslovi, a i poradi interesot vo gradot za {koluvawe na vakvi deca, vo u~ebnata 1953/54 godina **se otvori prvoto oddelenie za vakvi deca vo osnovnoto u~ili{te "Kole Kaninski", a vedna{ potoa i vo osnovnite u~ili{ta "Goce Del~ev" i "Trifun Panovski" vo Bitola**

Neposredno so zgolemuvawe brojot na posebnite oddelenija pri spomnatite u~ili{ta i pritisokot za otvorawe posebni oddelenija, osobeno vo Skopje, bea formirani gol em broj posebni oddelenija i vo drugi gradovi:

Vo u~ebnata 1956/57 godina se otvori ja dve posebni oddelenija pri OU "Bra}a Ribar", a vo 1959/60 godina i pri OU "Jane Sandanski" i edno posebno oddelenie pri OU "Stiv Naumov" - Skopje.

children and youth was established in Banja Bansko – Strumica. The conceptual, organizational, technical-technological, as well as personnel enabled implementation of the following activities: **board and lodging, elementary and secondary school education, work training and professional qualification, rehabilitation treatment (psycho-motor therapy, hydrotherapy, physical therapy, electrotherapy, paraffin therapy, spa therapy) and health care.** (4)

5. Care, education and rehabilitation for people with psychic disabilities

The institutionalized system for care, education and rehabilitation of people with easy, moderate, hard and severe psychic disabilities is presented according to the institutions.

ELEMENTARY SCHOOL EDUCATION FOR CHILDREN WITH EASY PSYCHIC DISABILITIES

Classes for children with psychic disabilities, which were part of the "Institute for Disabled Children" in Bitola, due to inappropriate conditions and interest in the town for education of such children, in the school year 1953/54 **the first grade class for such children was opened within the formal elementary school "Kole Kaninski" and later in the schools "Goce Delchev" and "Trifun Panovski" in Bitola.**

After the increased number of special classes at the mentioned schools and the pressure for opening special classes, especially in Skopje, such special classes were opened within other formal schools in different towns:

In the school year 1956/57 two special classes at the elementary school "Bra}a Ribar" and in 1959/60 one at the elementary school "Jane Sandanski", as well as one at the elementary school "Stiv Naumov" in Skopje was opened.

- **Vo isto vreme bea otvoreni posebni oddelenija pri OU "Kliment Ohridski# vo Prilep i vo OU "Trajko Andreev# vo Veles. Ne{ to podocna vo u-ebnata 1975/76 godina bea otvoreni posebni paralelki pri redovnoto OU "Manu{ Turnovski# vo Novo Selo - Strumi~ko.**

Nepodgotvenosta na redovnite osnovni u-ili{ tata za adekvatno prifa}awe, na decata so lesna psihi~ka popre~enost da u-at zaedno so decata bez pre~ki vo razvojt i neobezbedenosta na stru~no-def ekto lo{ ki kadri, nu`no se nametna potreba od prezemawe merki za sozdavawe adekvatni uslovi za rabota so formirawe posebni u-ili{ ta. Be formirani **specijalnite osnovni u-ili{ ta za deca so lesna psihi~ka popre~enost "Marko Cepenkov# vo Prilep (1966/67), "Makarenko# vo Bitola (1967/68), "Idnina# (1971/72) i "Dr Zlatan Sremac# (1972/73) vo Skopje, "Maca Ovcharova# vo Veles (1971/72) i specijalno u-ili{ te so u-eni~ki dom za deca so lesna i umerena psihi~ka popre~enost "25 Maj# - sega "Sv. Kliment Ohridski# - (1985/86) vo Novo Selo - Strumi~ko, kako edinstvena ustanova vo zenjata za deca koi nemat uslovi da stekot osnovno obrazovane vo svoite mesta na `iveewe. (3)**

Specijalnite u-ili{ ta vo Prilep i Bitola se zatvorija. Namesto ni v prodol`ija so rabota posebni oddelenija pri redovni osnovni u-ili{ ta, dodeka drugite ~etiri specijalni u-ili{ ta vo Skopje, Veles i Novo Selo prodol`ija ponatamu so rabota.

Osnovni karakteristiki na sovremenata koncepcija i praktika za rehabilitacija na ovie deca vo ovoj period bea: racionalizacija na edukativno-habilitacioni proces so paralelno dejstvuvawe na def ekto lo{ ki ot, psiholo{ ki ot i medicinski ot kadar; nastojuvawe da se kompletira tretmanot so neophodni te komponenti, maksimalna diferencijacija na ustanovite, klasifikacija na slu~ai te i popolnuvawe na ustanovite so potrebni ot def ekto lo{ ki kadar.

- **At the same time, special classes at the elementary school "Kliment Ohridski" in Prilep and the elementary school "Trajko Andreev" in Veles were opened. In the school year 1975/76, special classes were opened within the elementary school "Manush Turnovski" in Novo Selo, Strumica.**

Formal elementary schools were not ready for adequate acceptance of children with easy psychic disabilities to have classes together with children without developmental disabilities. Lack of professional special teachers imposed the need for undertaking measures to establish adequate conditions for work in special schools. Special elementary schools for children with easy psychic disabilities were formed: "Marko Cepenkov" in Prilep (1966/67), "Makarenko" in Bitola (1967/68), "Idnina" (1971/72) and "Dr. Zlatan Sremac" (1972/73) in Skopje, "Maca Ovcharova" in Veles (1971/72) and Specialized school with boarding house for children with easy and moderate psychic disabilities "25 Maj", now "Sv. Kliment Ohridski" (1985/86) in Novo Selo, Strumica, as unique institution in the country for education of children from different parts of the country where special classes could not be organized. (3)

Special schools in Prilep and Bitola were closed and special classes continued in formal elementary schools, while the other four special schools in Skopje, Veles and Novo Selo continued to work.

Basic characteristics of contemporary conception and practice for rehabilitation of these children during this period were: rationalization of education and habilitation process parallel to the activities of special education and rehabilitation, psychological and medical staff; trying to complete the treatment with necessary components, maximal differentiation of the institutions, classification of cases and equipping the institutions with special education staff.

SREDNO OBRAZOVANI E ZA MLADINCI SO
LESNA PSIHI^KA POPRE^ENOST

[ireweto na mre`ata na osnovni u~ili{ta, odnosno oddelenija za osnovno obrazovanje za decata so lesna psihi~ka popre~enost, kako i s pogolemiot broj u~enici { to go zavr{uvaa ova obrazovanie, go aktueliziraa problemot za srednoto obrazovanie. Poradi toa u~ili{tata za osnovno obrazovanie, dru{tvata za pomo{ na licata so psihi~ka popre~enost i stru~nite slu`bi pri nadle`nite organi na upravata vo zemjata, pravea napori da se re{ i ovoj problem. Se predlo`ija soodvetni re{enija od koi najpovolno be{e otvoraweto sredni u~ili{ta za mladinci so lesna psihi~ka popre~enost, vo koi }e se izveduva i teoretskiot i prakti~niot del na nastavata. Organiziranoto sredno obrazovanie za ovi e mladinci po~na vo **Centarot za rehabilitacija i obrazovanie "Makedonija# - sega "Sv. Naum Ohridski #- Skopje i vo Centarot za sredno obrazovanie "Iskra# - [tip za lica so lesna psihi~ka popre~enost. (5)**

REHABILITACIJA ZA LICA SO UMERENA
PSIHI^KA POPRE^ENOST

Prvite razmisluvawa za organizirano po~nuvawe so za{tita i rehabilitacija za lica so umerena psihi~ka popre~enost kaj nas datiraat od 1957, odnosno od 1962 godina vo analizite i istra`uvawata { to se napravija od stru~nata slu`ba pri toga{niot republi~ki organ za socijalna politika.

- **Vo 1962 godina Izvr{niot sovet na SRM donese re{enie za osnovawe ustanova za rabota so lica so umerena psihi~ka popre~enost, koja po~na so rabota vo adaptirane prostorii na porane{ata ustanova za slepi lica vo Dra~evo (1963 godina);**
- **Vo 1970 godina, otkako se izgradija novite namenski prostorii vo Skopje, ustanovata se preseli vo niv i po~na so rabota vrz nova sovremena koncepcija i organizacija pod naziv "Zavod za rehabilitacija na deca i mladinci #.**

SECONDARY EDUCATION OF YOUTH WITH EASY
PSYCHIC DISABILITIES

Spreading of the elementary school network, i.e. classes for elementary education for children with easy psychic disabilities, as well as bigger number of children completing this education initiated the issue of the secondary school education. The elementary schools, associations for assistance to people with psychic disabilities and professional services at the state organs in the country tried to solve that issue. Among the proposed appropriate solutions, the most convenient was opening of secondary schools for youth with easy psychic disabilities, including theoretical and practical part of the educational process. The organized secondary school education for those students started in: **Center for Rehabilitation and Education "Makedonija" – now " Sv. Naum Ohridski" in Skopje and Center for Secondary School education "Iskra" – Shtip for people with easy psychic disabilities. (5)**

REHABILITATION OF PEOPLE WITH EASY PSY-
CHIC DISABILITIES

The first thoughts for organizing care and rehabilitation for people with moderate psychic disabilities in our country date from 1957, i.e. 1962 in analyses and research made by the professional service of republic organs for social policy.

- **In 1962, the Executive Council of Socialistic Republic of Macedonia brought a decision for establishing institution for people with moderate psychic disabilities, which started work in adapted premises within the previous Institution for blind people in Drachevo (1963);**
- **In 1970, after the new premises were built in Skopje, the institution moved there and started work with new contemporary conception and organization as "Institute for Rehabilitation of Children and Youth".**

Toa be{ e prva specializirana ustanova za vakvi lica za za{ tita, edukacija i rehabilitacija vrz sovremena nau~na osnova vo na{ ata zemja so izveduvawe na: **opservacija, dijagnostika i klasifikacija, evidencija i statistika; preventiva na podra-jeto na psihi~kata popre~nost; terapevtski (korektivno-habilitaciski) tretman; edukacija, odnosno elementarno osnovno obrazovanie; rabotna orientacija, rabotno osposobuvawe vo industrijska, zanaet~iska, zenjodelska i `ivinarska nasoka; zgri`uvawe, vospituvawe i smestuvawe; zdravstvena za{ tita; sovetodavna rabota so roditelite na vakvite deca i mladinci.**

Za izvr{ uvawe na ovie dejnosti Zavodot gi ima{ e slednive organizaciski edinici: **opservaciono-dijagnosti~ka edinica so sovetovali{ te; edinica za habilitaciono-korekcionen tretman; laboratorisko-istra`uva~ka edinica so biohemiska i citogenetska laboratorija; edinica-gradinka za predri~ili{ no vospituvawe; edinica-u-ili{ te za elementarno osnovno obrazovanie; edinica za edukacija, odnosno za habilitaciono-korekciona rabota so umereno psihi~ki popre~eni deca i so pote{ ki rastrojstva vo sluhot i govorot; edinica-u-ili{ te za rabotna orientacija, kako i za rabotno osposobuvawe vo odelni rabotni organizacii vo industrijska i zanaet~iska rabota; edinica za rabotno osposobuvawe vo zenjodelstvoto (gradinarstvo, ovo{tarstvo i `ivinarstvo); stacionar so kabinet za doma}instvo, ambulanta i izolaciono odlelenie.**

Organizacijata na ustanovata, a osobeno izveduvaweto na rehabilitacioni ot proces, be{ e postaveno vrz sovremeni osnovi od steknatoto iskustvo, od napravenite specializacii vo svetot i koristej}i gi sovremenite dostignuvawa pri sposobeni na na{ i te uslovi.

That was the first specialized institution for such people in our country for care, education and rehabilitation on contemporary scientific basis, implementing the following: **observation, diagnosis and classification; evidence and statistics; prevention in the field of psychic disabilities; therapeutic (correction and habilitation) treatment; education, i.e. elementary school education; work orientation, work training in industry, trade, agriculture and poultry raising division; care, education and lodging; health care; consultations with parents of such children and youth.**

For performing these activities, the institution had the following organization units: **observation and diagnosis unit with counseling service; unit for habilitation and correction treatment; laboratory and research unit with biochemistry and cito-genetic laboratory; kindergarten with preschool education unit; elementary school education unit; unit for habilitation and correction treatment of children with moderate psychic disabilities and with severe impairments of hearing and speech; unit - school for work orientation, as well as work training in different work organizations in industry and trade; unit for work training in agriculture (gardening, fruit growing and poultry raising); dispensary with cabinet for household, ambulance and isolation section.**

The organization of the institution and especially implementation of the rehabilitation process was set up on contemporary basis and gained experience, specializations in the world and contemporary achievements adapted in our environment.

ZA[TI TA, HABI LI TACI ONEN I KOREKCI ONEN TRETMAN ZA LI CA SO TE[KA I DLABOKA PSI HI ^KA POPRE^ENOST

Prvite razmislavawa za posebno organizirana za[tita na lica so te[ka i dlaboka psihi~ka popre~enost gi zabele`uvame vo izgotveni ot materijal od stru~nata slu`ba pri republi~ki ot organ za socijalna politika vo 1957 godina. **So re[e nie na I zvr[ni ot sovet na NRM vo 1958 godi na be[e formirana ustanova za lica so te[ka i najte[ka (dlaboka) psihi~ka popre~enost, so naziv "Specijalen zavod# so sedi [te vo Demir Kapija** So toa prvpat vo na[ata zemja be[e po~nata organizirana insti tucional na def ekto lo[ka za[tita i tretman za takvi lica kako dejnost vo oblata na socijalnata za[tita, koja raboti i denes. **Prvite korisnici vo Zavodot bea prezemeni od du[evnite bolnici od Bardovci i Demir Hisar i od se mejstvata kade [to tie pretstavuvaa te`ok socijal en problem**

Vo po~etni ot period ustanovata ima[e prete`no azilski karakter, a podocna se izmeni so podobruvawe na uslovi te za rabota i anga`irawe stru~ni kadri od razli~ni profili: **lekari, terapeviti, medicinski sestri i negovatelki, defektolozi, instruktori za rabotno osposobuvawe, socijalni rabotnici i drugi**.

Sodr`inata na tretmanot se z bogatuvaw e so sovremeni soznani ja od oblata na socijalnata, zdravstvenata i def ekto lo[ka ta praktika, pri [to sevkupni ot proces primi humanitaren, za[titen i habilitacionen karakter. Toa osobeno mo`e[e da se zabele`i so otvorawe na Depandans pri ovoj Zavod za lica so te[ka psihi~ka popre~enost vo 1970 godina, kade [to se organiziraa: **vospitni grupi spored vozrasta i stepenot na preostanatite psihofizi~ki sposobnosti za steknuvawe elementarno vospitatie i obrazovanie i rabotni grupi od mladinci za opredeleni rabotni oeracii vo rabotilnici (tkawe, pleteve, vezewe, [iewe i dr.) i vo zenjodelstvoto (gradinarstvo, lozarstvo, `ivinarstvo, sto~arstvo i sl.).**

CARE, HABILITATION AND CORRECTION TREATMENT OF PEOPLE WITH SEVERE AND DEEP PSYCHIC DISABILITIES

The first thoughts for special organized care for people with severe and deep psychic disabilities are noticed in the material prepared by professional service at republic organ for social policy in 1957. **With decision of the Executive Council of People's Republic of Macedonia in 1958, an institution for people with severe and deep psychic disabilities called "Special Institute "in Demir Kapija was formed.** That marked the beginning of organized institutional special education and rehabilitation process for such people in the field of social care.

The first beneficiaries in the Institute were brought from mental hospitals in Bardovci and Demir Hisar and from families where they presented a difficult social problem.

At the beginning, the institution had mostly asylum character and later it changed and improved its conditions of work and engaged professional staff from different profiles: **doctors, therapists, nurses; special teachers, instructors for work training; social workers and others.**

The content of the treatment was enriched with contemporary knowledge in the field of social, health and special education and rehabilitation practice, and the process itself acquired humanitarian, protective and habilitation character. That was noticeable when the Branch at the Institute for people with severe psychic disabilities in 1970 was opened implementing the following: **education group according to the age and the level of the left psychic abilities for elementary education and work group for youth for determined work operations in workshops (weaving, knitting, embroidering, sawing and other) and in agriculture (gardening, wine growing, poultry raising, cattle breeding etc.).**

Vo 1970 godina tretmanot i za licata so dlaboka psihi~ka popre~enost be{ e organiziran na pohumani i posovremeni za{ titni osnovi. Se vovede: **zdravstvena za{ tita (internisti~ka, ginekolo{ ka, stonatalo{ ka, rentgenolo{ ka i drugi zdravstveni slu` bi); pravilna ishrana i samposlo` uvawe i habilitacisko-terapevtska rabota (rabotna okupacija, fizioterapija, muzikoterapija i dr.).** (3)

Institucionaliziraweto na za{ titata, edukacijata, osposobuwaweto i rehabilitacijata za licata so psihi~ka popre~enost vo Republika Makedonija pretstavuva vtemel uvawe i razvoj na oligofrenologijata kako avtenti~na nau~na disciplina na defektologijata.

Professionalno orientirawe, rabotno osposobuwawe, profesionalna kvalifikacija i vrabotuvawe za lica so invalidnost

Ako se napravi analiza na organizacijskata postavenost, kako i na dejnosti te na site defektolo{ki ustanovi kaj nas, }e se vidi deka socijalnata komponenta na predmetot na defektologijata e zastapena u{ te vo nivni ot nikul ec. **Vo niv bea zastapeni: profesionalnata i rabotna orientacija, profesionalnata okvalifikuvawe i rabotnoto osposobuwawe.**

Sostojbata na psihofizi~kite sposobnosti, karakterot napre~enosta i stepenot na osposobenosta za rabota, ja nametnaa potrebatata od prezemawe merki za adekvatno vkluvawe na licata so invalidnost vo rabotni ot proces. **Po~na vrabotuvawe vo stopanski organizacii, vo organizacijski edini ci od zatvoren tip i grupno i pojedine~no vkluvawe vo otvoreno stopanstvo.** Be{ e sozdadena mre`a od specijalizirani rabotni organizacii "za{ titni rabotilnici #i "za{ titni rabotni organizacii #koi sozdadoa praktika i pomognaa kvalitetno da se izmeni javnoto mislewe za mo`nosti te, vakvata populacija da bi de vkluv~ena vo proizvodstveni ot proces i da se integri ra vo socijalnata sredi na. (4)

In 1970, the treatment for people with deep psychic disabilities was organized in more human and more contemporary conditions. The following was introduced: **health care (internal medicine, gynecology, stomatology, X-ray and other health services); healthy nutrition and self-service and habilitation-therapeutic work (work occupation, physical therapy, musical therapy etc.).** (3)

Institutionalization for care, education, training and rehabilitation of people with psychic disabilities in the Republic of Macedonia is the foundation and development of oligophrenology as an authentic scientific discipline of special education and rehabilitation.

Professional orientation, work training, professional qualification and employment of people with disabilities

If analysis for organizational structure is made, as well as the activities of all special education and rehabilitation institutions in our country, it will be noticed that the social component of special education and rehabilitation was present even in their beginning. **These institutions implemented: professional and work orientation; professional qualification and work training.**

The condition of psycho-physical abilities, the character of disabilities and the level of work qualification imposed the need for undertaking measures for adequate inclusion of people with disabilities in the working process. **Employment in working organizations, in organizational units of closed type and group and individual inclusion in the open economy started.** Special working organization network was established: "shelter workshops" and "shelter work organizations" with practice which qualitatively changed public opinion

about the possibilities such population to be included in the process of production and in social environment. (4)

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